

Mendeley

Management Reference Mendeley dan Zotero

Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto

Directed by

Jurusan Akuakultur

Universitas Bangka Belitung

Selasa, 7 November 2023

MENDELEY
ADVISOR ID

Profil

Nama : Eko Wahyu Nur Sofianto

ORCID ID : [0000-0002-2607-5567](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2607-5567)

Scopus ID: 57211919231

Editorin Chief Tarbiyah: Jurnal Ilmiah
Kependidikan (Sinta 4)

Tutor Relawan Jurnal Indonesia Provinsi
Kalimantan Selatan (Ketua Divisi Akreditasi
dan Indeksasi)

Email: ekowahyu@relawanjurnal.id

Blogger ekowahyu

Phone: 085736023858

Mengapa menggunakan tools “Mendeley” dan “Zotero”

1. Format “Mazab” Primer dan Mutakhir
2. Konsisten
3. Menghindari referensi “tidak dikutip”
4. Data rujukan tersimpan dalam library online

Posisi Tools Mendeley/ Zotero dalam karya ilmiah

1. Title
 - a. Abstrak
 - b. Kata Kunci
 2. Introduction
 3. Method
 4. Result and Discussion
 5. Bibliografi
 - a. Citation
 - b. Bibliografi
-] → Mendeley/ Zotero

Mendeley

1. Mendeley menggunakan dua cara yaitu mendeley desktop dan fitur terbaru yaitu Mendeley Reference Manager
2. Mendeley desktop sampai saat ini masih bisa digunakan
3. Mendeley Reference Manager yang dirilis tahun 2019 menggunakan aplikasi add on pada ms word
4. Mendeley tidak lagi ada profil tetapi langsung masuk di mendeley library

Mendeley

The screenshot shows the Mendeley website's download page for Windows. The browser address bar displays "mendeley.com/download-desktop-new/". The page header includes the Mendeley logo, navigation links for "Solutions", "Support", "Sign In", and "Create account", and a "Download" button. The main heading is "Download Mendeley Desktop for Windows". Below this is an illustration of a laptop with a Windows logo on the screen and a Mendeley icon in a dashed circle. A red button labeled "Download Mendeley Desktop for Windows" is positioned below the illustration. Underneath the button, the text reads "Windows 7, 8.1 and 10 (Version 1803) [See release notes.](#)". Further down, it says "Other systems:" followed by links for "Mendeley Desktop for macOS" (with an Apple logo) and "Mendeley Desktop for Linux" (with a Linux penguin logo). At the bottom of the page, a blue banner contains the text "New Mendeley Reference Manager is now available" and a white "Get started" button.

Mendeley

The screenshot shows the Mendeley website's download page for the Reference Manager. The browser address bar displays "mendeley.com/download-reference-manager". The page features the Mendeley logo and navigation links for Solutions, Support, Sign In, Create account, and a Download button. The main heading is "Mendeley Reference Manager", followed by a prominent "Download now for Windows" button. Below this, it specifies "Windows 7 and above" and provides a link to "See release notes". An illustration of a laptop with the Mendeley logo on the screen and a document is shown. A section for "Other Systems" includes links for "Mendeley Reference Manager for macOS" (with an Apple logo) and "Mendeley Reference Manager for Linux" (with a penguin logo). A note states "Mendeley Desktop is still available" with a "Learn more" link. The bottom section is titled "Your new Mendeley Reference Manager" and features icons representing document management and a partially visible "Activate" link.

Mendeley

← → ↻ mendeley.com/reference-manager/library/all-references/ 🔍 ☆ 📄 🗨️ ⚙️ ☰ 👤

Library | Notebook 🔄 👤 Eko Sofianto ▾

[+Add new](#)

All References 🔍 Search ☰

<input type="checkbox"/>	AUTHORS	YEAR	TITLE	SOURCE	ADDED ▾	FI
<input type="checkbox"/>	Fratiwi, N. J. D	2017	The Transformation of Two-Tier Test into Fourtier Test on Newton's...	AIP Conference Proce...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Goszewski, Matthew., Moyer, Adam., Baza...	2012	Exploring Student Difficulties with Pressure in a Fluid.	PERC Proceedings	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ichtiyaranisa, U, Tandililing, E, & Oktavian...	2013	Remediasi Kesalahan Siswa Menyelesaikan Soal Fluida Statis Me...	Jurnal Pendidikan dan ...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gurel, D. K., & Eryilmaz A	2015	A Review and Comparison of Diagnostic Instruments to Identify St...	Eurasia Journal of Mat...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Dewinta Oktaviana, Sri Hartini D	2017	Pengembangan Modul Fisika Berintegerasi Kearifan Lokal Membu...	Berkala Ilmiah Penddi...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Jufridaa, Basukia F, Pratiwia D	2018	The Potential of Local Wisdom on Traditional Fishing (Tangkul) Ge...	Scientiae Educatia: Ju...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Setiawan B, Innatesari D, Sabtiawan W, S...	2017	The Development of Local Wisdom-Based Natural Science Modul...	Jurnal Pendidikan IPA ...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Subali, B, Sopyan, A E	2015	Pengembangan Desain Pembelajaran Sains Berbasis Kearifan Lo...	Jurnal Pendidikan Fisi...	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Mochammad Yasir, Wulandari A, Qomaria ...	2020	The Contribution of Local Wisdom Integrated Science Learning M...	Jurnal Bioedukatika	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Maria Waldetrudis Lidi	2019	Ragam Implementasi Materi Lokal Melalui Komponen-komponen ...	Jurnal Dinamika Sains	09/05/2021	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Aji Saputra, Sri Wahyuni R	2016	Pengembangan Modul IPA Berbasis Kearifan Lokal Daerah Pesisir...	Jurnal Pembelajaran F...	09/05/2021	

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Mendeley

Mendeley Desktop

File Edit View Tools Help

Add Folders Related Sync Help

Search...

Eko

Mendeley

Literature Search

My Library

- All Documents
- Recently Added
- Recently Read
- Favorites
- Needs Review
- My Publications
- Unsorted
- Creativity Thinking

Filter by Authors

All

- , Achmad Samsudin, David Edison Tarigan, Id...
- , Ibrahim
- Abad-Corpa, Eva
- Abdullah, Zaini
- Abdurrahman, Abdurrahman
- Abel, Mara
- Abidin Pasaribu, Saparini
- Access, Open
- Adams, Tony E
- Advogados, Costa
- Afzal, A., dan Rohman, A
- Ahmadi, Fazlolaah

All Documents Edit Settings

★	●	📄	Authors	Title
☆	●		Fратиwi, N. J., dkk.	The Transformation of Two-Tier Test into Fourtier Test of Newton's laws concepts.
☆	●		Goszewski, Matthew., Moyer, Adam., Bazan, Zach ary, & ...	Exploring Student Difficulties with Pressure in a Fluid.
☆	●		Ichtiyaranisa, U, Tandililing, E, & Oktavianty, E.	Remediasi Kesalahan Siswa Menyelesaikan Soal Fluida Statis Menggunakan Model Make A Match di SMA
☆	●		Gurel, D. K., & Eryilmaz, A.	A Review and Comparison of Diagnostic Instruments to Identify Students' Misconceptions in Science
☆	●		Dewinta Oktaviana, Sri Hartini, dan Misbah	Pengembangan Modul Fisika Berintegerasi Kearifan Loka Membuat Minyak Lala untuk Melatih Karakter Sanggam
☆	●		Jufridaa; Basukia, Fibrika Rahmat; Pratiwia, dan Dwi ...	The Potential of Local Wisdom on Traditional Fishing (Tangkal) Gear in Lake Sipin Jambi City as a Science Lear
☆	●		Setiawan, B.; Innatesari, D. K.; Sabtiawan, W. B.; Sudar...	The Development of Local Wisdom-Based Natural Science Module to Improve Science Literation of Students
☆	●		Subali, B, Sopyan, A, Ellianawati	Pengembangan Desain Pembelajaran Sains Berbasis Kearifan Lokal untuk Mengembangkan Karakter Positif di
☆	●		Mochammad Yasir, Wulandari, Ana Yuniasti Retno; Qomari...	The Contribution of Local Wisdom Integrated Science Learning Model to Students' Scientific Communication Sk
☆	●		Maria Waldetrudis Lidi	Ragam Implementasi Materi Lokal Melalui Komponen-komponen Pembelajaran dalam Pembelajaran Sains
☆	●		Aji Saputra, Sri Wahyuni, Rifati Dina Handayani	Pengembangan Modul IPA Berbasis Kearifan Lokal Daerah Pesisir Puger pada Pokok Bahasan Sistem Transportasi c
☆	●		Suryanti Suryanti, Neni Mariana, Yoyok Yermiandho...	Local Wisdom-Based Teaching Material for Enhancing Primary Students' Scientific Literacy Skill

Details Notes Contents

No documents selected

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

Mendeley

1. Pengguna mendeley wajib memiliki akun Microsoft bisa online atau office 365 dsb
2. Tahapan untuk MRM yaitu Download aplikasi MRM-login ke aplikasi MRM-klik Mendeley cite for Microsoft word-logo akan terpasang di paling kanan-login ke mendeley cite-akan diarahkan ke akun mircosoft

Mendeley

Zotero

zotero.org/download/

Welcome, [ekowahyu](#) · [Settings](#) · [Inbox](#) · [Download](#) · [Log Out](#)

[Home](#) [Web Library](#) [Groups](#) [People](#) [Documentation](#) [Forums](#) [Get Involved](#)

[Home](#) > Downloads

Zotero 5.0 for Windows

Your personal research assistant

[Download](#)

Zotero Connector

Save to Zotero from your browser

[Install Chrome Connector](#)

Zotero Connectors automatically sense content

MENDELEY
ADVISOR ID

Activate Windows
MILLAWAN
JURNAL INDONESIA

Zotero

zotero

Web Library Groups Documentation Forums Get Involved ekowahyu

Q Title, Creator, Year

Upgrade Storage

My Library

- Creativity
- Miskonsepsi
- S1877042814006211
- My Publications
- Trash

adobe flash cs3 professional
al-Samargandi ayat-ayat al-quran Beck
Borel resumability
computer-assisted learning
cooperative learning Critical thinking
Deep Learning Distributed Random Forest
Filter Tags

Title	Creator	Date
2013-18854-1-PB.pdf		
2013-Dec-25-Open-Access--Education-Journals-and...		
2165-5109-1-PB.pdf		
987-1404719938.pdf		
A Comparison of Creative Thinking Abilities of High ...	Anwar et al.	2012
Abdul Manan Bin Mohamad & Kamaruddin Salleh (...)		
Abdul Shukor Hj. Husin (2008). Pembangunan Musli...		
Ajmaain@ Jamaain Safar & Ramli Awang (2008). Sej...		
Alwan, A.A. Misconception of Heat and Temperature...		
An Assimilation-Based Model for Preventing Religio...		
An Assimilation-Based Model for Preventing Religio...		
ANALISIS Miskonsepsi Suhu dan Kalor pada Si...		
ANALISIS Pemahaman Konsep Siswa SMA Neger...		
ANALISIS Pemahaman Konsep Siswa SMA Neger...		
ANALISIS Pemahaman Konsep Siswa SMA Neger...		

Info Notes Tags Attachments Related

Item Type Book

Title

Author last name, first name

Series

Series Number

Volume

of Volumes

Edition

Place

Publisher

Date

of Pages

Language

ISBN

Short Title

URL

Accessed

Archive

Loc. in Archive

Library Catalog

Call Number

Rights

Extra

Zotero

Mendeley

감사합니다 Natick
 Danke Ευχαριστίες Dalu
 Grazie Thank You Köszönöm
 Спасибо Dank Gracias
 谢谢 Merci Seé
 ありがとう
 Obrigado

MENDELEY
ADVISOR ID

iji RELAWAN
JURNAL INDONESIA